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**HEALTH SAVING EDUCATION AT SCHOOLS
OF POLAND (70–80-ies OF XX CENTURY)***

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**ЗДОРОВ'ЯЗБЕРЕЖУВАЛЬНЕ ВИХОВАННЯ У ШКОЛАХ ПОЛЬЩІ
(70–80-ті роки ХХ століття)***

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70-ies of the XX century was a turning point for Poland in the field of school education. Created by the Committee of Experts contributed to the development and implementation of educational proposals and concepts for the modernization of the school system in Poland, including in the field of health saving of schoolchildren. It was determined that the cooperation of the Ministry of Education and Training and the Ministry of Health and Social Care in Poland contributed to the development health saving education in educational institutions of the country through regulations and programs for a healthy person of schoolchildren. It was found that in 70–80 years of the XX century, health saving education was actively supported both by the state, through the adoption of certain documents, and on the part of scientists. It was analyzed the authors' concepts and programs on creating a culture of health of schoolchildren through the health saving education.

Key words: school, health saving education, process, health saving upbringing, health culture.

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Formulation of the problem. Analysis of key studies and publications.

Creating a safe and comfortable environment for training and education of schoolchildren is one of the main factors to preserve their lives and health. The educational process at school is built mainly on the scientific basis of hygiene that promotes efficiency, achieve higher results in school. In this regard, on the lessons are used types and forms of educational activities, techniques and technology education according to the level of psychophysical development, constitutional features of schoolchildren.

Thus, health saving upbringing and health saving education, which was partially implemented in schools in Poland in the study period, became a vivid example of solving health saving of individuality of schoolchild.

Analysis of the Polish educational literature showed that by the scientists the 70's of XX century was studied the issue of health saving of schoolchildren in different directions. The presence at the school proper conditions for the formation of a healthy individuality of a child (E. Gzhyvashevska M. Kvarchynskyy, B. Kozhushnik, E. Polus-Shenyavska), health saving education as a necessary component of a culture of health of schoolchildren (M. Demel, I. Kavetsky, B. Kozhushnik, H. Malushevskyy, S. Radukevych, H. Ventlandtova), microclimate of school rooms (V. Balinskaya, J. Groba, C. Korczak, I. Shpakovych). The scientists noted that health saving education should be directed as students' and teachers' attention to develop their habits and skills and understanding the key provisions for healthy living, forming in them a culture of health. A special role is given to the teacher, because he is the leading fellow of health saving education at school.

In addition, health saving education is primarily a process of comprehensive educational work, which involves the definition of health as the highest value, the formation of the younger generation of healthy lifestyles and health saving [13].

The global importance and the urgency of preserving the health of young people caused concernment not only the leading representatives of the Polish, but also the world of science of the study period. In particular, it has been taken a number of documents, materials and recommendations of the Council of Europe, the World Health Organization, which show considerable attention in Europe to ensure healthy growth generation ("Measurement of levels of health", 1979; Madrid Conference of European Health Ministers, 1981; conference "European approach to health care" (Sweden), 1981; Guidelines for developing health education programs of population, 1981; Ottawa Charter, 1986, etc.).

This activity actively participated by the International Union for Health Education, the Council of the European Network of Health Promoting Schools and the Commission of the European Communities, as evidenced by annual events devoted to the issue of healthy lifestyles, particularly among young people: “Prepare for a healthy lifestyle in the society” (Hall, 1981); “Teaching youth smoking cessation and alcohol dependence” (Vienna, 1982); “Prospects for youth health promotion in the European region” (Germany, 1983); “Education in the School of Health in the European Region” (France, 1984).

Purpose of the article is to reveal features of implementation of health saving education of the schoolchildren at schools in Poland in the 70–80-ies of the XX century.

Problem statement. Analysis of laws and government regulations, theoretical developments and scientific expertise of teachers, practitioners, archival sources and periodicals [1; 3; 4; 7; 9] shows that in the 70s of the XX century Poland had made a significant breakthrough in the development of school policies. Moreover, according to UNESCO that time Poland was “a country of people who study” and was able to prepare staff without whom the rebuilding and developing of the country destroyed by the war would be impossible. Thus, the Committee of Experts was created, which was developed proposals and educational concepts to modernize the school system in Poland based on two years’ analysis of the existing education system. The Committee invited representatives of scientific field, namely 23 leading scientists (mostly professors), teachers-innovators and public figures, that was not in other countries of the socialist bloc and, accordingly, has caused great interest in Western and Eastern Europe (by this time it was thought that enough to follow the example of the Soviet Union and implement the theoretical principles of Marxist theory). Results of Committee work was published in two publications: “Regulations and abstracts about the state of education in Polish People’s Republic” (February, 1973) and “The report on the state of education in Polish People’s Republic” (May, 1973). In particular, it was emphasized that the current school system requires a deep reform, particularly in the direction of bringing the content of training programs for practical social requirements, training and education “in life and through life”, improving the existing framework of schools and material support of teachers, introduction to teaching practice innovation [12].

As a result, the Report of Committee of Experts, which was discussed outside the country, and the Report have acquired interest from the general

public and active public discussion, which was attended by 200 thousand people. The document itself and its findings were the basis for the adoption by the Sejm of the Polish People's Republic (PPR) October 13, 1973 resolution "On the system of public education", which was formulated by a leading concept of the school system. Note that in the "Resolution ..." was fixed positions on the formation and development of a healthy young generation state. First, attention was focused on the further development of the network of kindergartens, namely compulsory preschool education coverage of children 6 years of age in order to eliminate their existing gaps in mental and physical development. Second, it highlights the main factors the impact on the educational environment of a healthy individuality of schoolchildren [10; 12].

Due to the new requirements for school were initiated various measures to provide a proper status to health saving education in the school system. Thus, in a relatively short period (1973–1975) Ministry of Education and Training and the Ministry of health and social care of Poland issued decisions and programs to build healthy personality of schoolchildren and implementation of health saving education in the schools of the country: The decision on improving the health of children and youth activities in the field of health within health saving education (1973); The program to improve the health of children and young people and further development of health saving provision in schools and education and educational institutions in years 1973–1975; Program for working to improve the health factors in schools and education and educational institutions in years 1973–1975; The program to improve the system for making decisions needs of schoolchildren and schools (1973); Legislative program to implement health saving education in the elementary school and out of school (1982); Decision on creation of posts in schools the teacher-coordinator of school hygiene and health saving education (developed in 1973, introduced in 1980); Guidelines for the implementation of programs in education and health in primary and secondary school (1982). At the initiative of leading scientists of the country (V. Vatslavskyy, M. Demel, A. Lidtkie, M. Paprotska, R. Tshesnovskyy) and the Ministry of Education was held symposiums, conferences and seminars on the prospects for implementation health saving education in schools of the country.

The result of this interest of the state by health saving of growing generation was also the adoption in 1973 by the Board of two ministries – Health care and Social protection and education and training to the decision to introduce school programs of health saving education [3; 6]. In connection with

the increased role of health saving education of schoolchildren and activity in this area of the state, PPR developed new concepts and complemented the existing 50-ies. On a culture of health of schoolchildren, which was an integral part health saving education.

Thus, T. Maleshevska has developed “model of a person” who is brought up with the main provisions of the concept of health culture. According to the researcher, it should be “flexible” man whose mind and work corresponds to the needs of the modern man, the requirements of society and the demands that are put in front of his life; it must be a person who is responsible for his own health and the health of others; versed in the characteristics of the individual in terms of the various sciences (pedagogy, medicine, psychology, sociology, etc.) [7].

In turn, J. Kohanek made some contributions to the development of the theory of schoolchildren health culture by involving schoolchild, especially of elementary school, in health saving education. In fact, according to the scientist, in elementary schools child’s personality is formed, laid the foundations of his future attitude to his own health and health of others: in elementary school child masters the basics of personal hygiene, occupational health and recreation as essential components of health [5]. On the basis of the school curriculum for elementary school J. Kohanek determined that the greatest opportunities for implementing health saving education has such subjects as natural, humanities, physical education, technical sessions, plastic lessons. On the lessons of these subjects, schoolchildren receive theoretical knowledge of hygiene that combines the practical psychosomatic development of the individual of a child.

In addition, with the support of famous Polish educator M. Demel, J. Kohanek proposed to organize in schools of the country “school health offices”, which would include support material for teachers, including tables, scientific articles, posters, movies filing, didactic games, audiovisual for training [1; 5].

Presented by aforementioned scientists theoretical proposals were refuted by C. Stypulovskyy. In his view, the study of questions of schoolchildren health culture formation through health saving education is lack of regularity, consistency and correlation of stages of training. Breaking question of health saving education problem, scholar stressed that the teaching process of health saving education system consists of components: schoolchild–teacher–education environment. However, at school, as usually, an effective interaction of these three components is missing, that is why health saving education of schoolchildren has a positive result.

In turn, scholars (V. Vatslavskyy, M. Paprotska, J. Jaworski) have created programs and projects on introduction health saving education at schools of the country to form, strengthen the health of the young generation.

Consider them in detail.

C. Stypulovskyy accumulated data from a culture of health of schoolchildren in the implementation of health saving education was systematized and reflected in the “Selected problems of health saving education of children and youth” in 1972/1973 academic year, the authors of which were M. Paprotska and V. Vatslavskyy [8]. It was a kind of a report on the problem of modeling health saving education for 10 years’ school, represented to the Department of Physical Education and the Institute of School Programs. The basis of the project was committed two conditions that meet the solemnity of implementation: comprehensive involvement of teachers, directors, school doctors to the social health problems outlined in the project time; age-appropriate schoolchildren and their interests according to age.

In 1977 the subject of the Polish educational community (M. Demel, J. Jaworski, B. Tvorek, I. Hembalchyk, A. Pavlutsky and others) was the interaction of physical culture and health culture as components of the educational process at school [1; 2; 4; 9; 11]. The discussion led to the draft program of J. Jaworski “Propaedeutics of health culture and physical culture in the education system. Outline of future models”. In June 1977 the conference were invited university experts in physical education and teacher education, representatives of institutions training teachers as competent consultants in the field of health saving and rehabilitation of the country population. J. Jaworski project was based on long-lived achievements of Polish and foreign scholars in the field of physical education of children of school age and analyzing the characteristics of subjects recreational areas. His goal was to find the means and methods appropriate measures a culture of health of schoolchildren in schools of the country. Besides, the goal of the program was identified the teaching of schoolchildren on practice use their knowledge on prevention health hazards, provide first aid through such cycles meaningful learning how to man and the environment; morpho-physiology of a man; motor activity of a man; personal and public hygiene; food hygiene; occupational health and recreation; safety and first aid. However, a few days before the conference, the project was removed from the discussion, because its content was significant competition concept curriculum of physical education, which was prepared by the Institute curricula of the Ministry of Education of Poland.

V. Vatslavsky was presented a project of a program of health saving education in school compared to other concepts of programs of the time [14]. A feature of this program was that it is based on three steps: a separate subject “Health saving education”; a set of physical education and health saving education; taking into account further developments of scholars in the field of health saving of younger generation.

Thus, designed during the 70-80-ies of XX century projects and programs of health saving education of schoolchildren have positive and negative aspects. On the one hand, proposed programs and projects have well-developed theoretical and practical aspects of their application. Their development was a kind of attempt to cause changes in thinking, proper evaluation and reassessment of negative values in life, the emergence of the necessary skills and the consequent formation of health saving behavior and healthy lifestyle. On the other hand, they do not receive further implementation, as required financing, developing new teaching of not only teachers and heads of secondary schools, but also for students – future teachers.

Conclusions. Thus, the idea of health saving education was attached by Polish state documents. The developed projects and programs have become the impetus for further development of the problem of health saving education. *Further study* is expected to conduct towards the study of the theory and practice of a culture of health of schoolchildren through the introduction of healthy education.

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Єрмакова Т. С. Здоров'язбережувальне виховання у школах Польщі (70-80-ті роки ХХ століття). 70-ті роки ХХ століття були для Польщі переламними у галузі шкільної освіти. Створений Комітет Експертів сприяв розробленню та впровадженню пропозицій та освітніх концепцій щодо модернізації системи шкільної освіти в Польщі, зокрема й у галузі здоров'язбереження школярів. Визначено, що співпраця Міністерства освіти і виховання та Міністерства здоров'я і суспільної опіки Польщі сприяла розвитку здоров'язбережувального виховання в загальноосвітніх закладах країни через ухвали та програми з формування здорової особистості школярів. Виявлено, що в 70-80-х роках ХХ століття здоров'язбережувальне виховання активно підтримувалося як з боку держави, через прийняття певних документів, так і з боку науковців. Проаналізовано авторські концепції та програми з питання формування культури здоров'я школярів через здоров'язбережувальне виховання.

Ключові слова: школа, здоров'язбережувальне виховання, формування, процес, здоров'язбережувальна освіта, культура здоров'я.

Ермакова Т. С. Здоровьесберегающее воспитание в школах Польши (70-80-ые годы XX столетия). 70-е годы XX века были для Польши переломными в области школьного образования. Созданный Комитет Экспертов способствовал разработке и внедрению предложений и образовательных концепций по модернизации системы школьного образования в Польше, в том числе и в области здоровьесбережения школьников. Определено, что сотрудничество Министерства образования и воспитания и Министерства здоровья и социального опеки Польши способствовало развитию здоровьесберегающего воспитания в общеобразовательных учреждениях страны через постановления и программы по формированию здоровой личности школьников. Выявлено, что в 70-80-х годах XX века здоровьесберегающее воспитание активно поддерживалось как со стороны государства, через принятие определенных документов, так и со стороны ученых. Проанализированы авторские концепции и программы по вопросу формирования культуры здоровья школьников через здоровьесберегающего воспитания.

Ключевые слова: школа, здоровьесберегающее воспитание, формирование, процесс, здоровьесберегающее образование, культура здоровья.